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A Smart Devices Concept for Future Soldier Systems

Topic 3: Implications of the Internet of Intelligent Things

Topic 5: Highly Connected, Automated, and Autonomous Forces

Topic 6: Interoperability, Integration and Security

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Abstract

The Internet-of-Things (IoT) promises to transform our society into smart environments that is environmentally aware. IoT applications cut across all societal domains, including military. Military organisations can exploit IoT applications in battlefields and operational theatres to improve situational awareness, mission performance and achieve information superiority.

In this paper, it is presented a concept for the application of smart devices and IoT to future soldier systems (FSS) at the tactical domain. Relevant information to be gathered includes location, health status, motion and characteristics of the surrounding environment. Using as reference the Norwegian Home Guard Area Force use case and prior work conducted by FFI, a first proof-of-concept (PoC) is described, including results from a demonstration action incorporating real and simulated nodes. The paper concludes with the presentation of next steps for this work, namely the upcoming collaboration with the NATO IST-150 Group, aiming to produce recommendations towards achieving interoperability involving smart devices and IoT concepts.

Index Terms — Smart Devices, IoT, Publish-Subscribe, Message Broker, MQTT, SOA, Web services, NATO.

1 Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) describes the revolution already under way that is seeing a growing number of internet enabled devices that can network and communicate with each other and with other web-enabled gadgets. IoT refers to a state where Things (e.g. objects, environments, vehicles and clothing) will have more and more information associated with them and may have the ability to sense, communicate, network and produce new information, becoming an integral part of the Internet. A widespread Internet of Things has the potential to transform how we live in our cities, how we move, how we develop sustainably, how we age, and more. -- From IoT Special Interest Group (Technology Strategy Board, 2013).

IoT promises to transform our society into smart environments, environmentally aware and well informed about its wellbeing, interests and security.

IoT is enabled by the convergence of several interdisciplinary domains including *networking, embedded hardware, radio spectrum, mobile computing, communication technologies, software architectures, sensing technologies, energy efficiency, information management, and data analytics* (Lamas *et al.*, 2016). Contributing to its growth and widespread adoption have been the rapid and continuous evolution on miniaturisation (smaller and lighter devices), connectivity (broadband) and energy efficiency, enabling the production of low-cost mobile equipment, such as smartphones.

IoT applications cut across all societal domains, including agriculture, energy, environment, health, industry, transportation, security and defence. IoT applications result from the deployment and connection of devices providing "live" data (about e.g., ambient temperature, energy consumption, device location, seismic activity, motion, video), processing capabilities and actuation (e.g., turn on/off bulb, increase room temperature, send audio to speaker, fire a smoke gun). Gartner estimates that 8.4 billion connected things will be in use worldwide by 2017 and will reach 20.4 billion by 2020 (Gartner, 2017); the presence of IoT devices will be ubiquitous and global.

As such, military organizations can (and should) exploit IoT environmental aware ecosystems deployed in battlefields and operational theatres to improve situational awareness, mission performance and achieve information superiority (Suri *et al.*, 2016). In fact, the currently active NATO IST-147 is investigating the military applications of IoT, including the exploitation of widely available low-cost IoT devices to gain competitive advantage in the military domain.

Aligned with these current trends, this paper develops a novel concept for the application of smart devices and IoT to FSS at the tactical domain. By incorporating smart devices in soldiers, it is possible to easily gather relevant information about e.g., location, health status, motion and surrounding environment. By connecting smart devices and applying IoT concepts, it becomes feasible to efficiently share (actionable) information and produce high levels of situational awareness at force level.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 ("Background") presents examples on the incorporation of smart devices and Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) equipment in FSS programmes, the involved challenges given the nature of tactical networks (as well as appropriate candidate communications technologies), associated security issues and relevant work conducted by FFI in the SMART experiment. Section 3 ("Concept") describes the novel concept for the application of smart devices and IoT to FSS at the tactical domain, using as reference the Norwegian Home Guard Area Forces use case and including the identification of smart devices and their mapping to FSS functions. Section 4

("Implementation and Deployment") presents the first steps implementing a proof-of-concept (PoC) to explore smart devices, COTS technologies and IoT concepts for FSS. The results from this first implementation and deployment are presented. The paper concludes with Section 5 ("Conclusion"), presenting the main results of the performed work and identifying next steps towards a large-scale deployment, as well as associated challenges. The paper closes with the supporting bibliography.

2 Background

FSS are present in R&D programmes of most countries, covering areas such as protection (e.g., bullet vests, CBRNe), mobility, sensors, smart weapons, health monitoring, information technologies and communications. For an extensive list of FSS programmes refer to (SoldierMod, 2017).

A common trend across FSS programmes consists in integrating miniaturized devices and information technologies in order to monitor soldier parameters that are mission relevant. In this regard, adopting a wide variety of low-cost yet high-performing COTS devices - such as those produced in the consumer mobile telecommunications and wearables industries - is becoming extremely appealing. Mobile devices like smartphones are powerful multipurpose platforms integrating multiple sensors, multimedia capabilities (audio, video, texting and display) and communications. In addition, despite their sophistication, end-users are already familiar with such devices, which enable them to be put to use with little additional training.

It is possible nowadays to see FSS components running on standard smartphones and operating systems like Android, Windows or iOS. To name a few:

- The U.S.A. Army Nett Warrior - an integrated dismounted situational awareness and mission command system - uses as end-user device a modified Samsung smartphone and a NSA-approved version of the Android operating system (Dixon and J. Henning, 2013). None of the radio components of the smartphone are used in this configuration and the smartphone becomes the centrepiece of a system with multiple components.
- In Norway, FFI worked on the "social tactical reporting system", whose focus was directed at the tactical edge and consumer technologies were employed. Commercial mobile networks were utilized communicating over the Internet using REST for messaging. Both a web-browser client and an Android native client were developed, but only the latter was relevant in a tactical environment, thus being selected for field experiments. Lessons learned from the CEI work (Karlsen and Reitan, 2014) and conducted experiments formed the basis of the next generation prototype developed by FFI, specifically, the SMART concept prototype (Johnsen *et al.*, 2017), which specifically targets the needs of the Norwegian Home Guard's Area Forces. SMART is further described later in this paper.

Nevertheless, incorporation of COTS technologies into the military market and, more specifically, at the tactical edge, brings several challenges that need to be addressed. For example, most COTS technologies are designed assuming broadband network access, while tactical networks are often analog or narrowband. Furthermore, they insufficiently handle privacy and security aspects, either by exposing data to third parties or by having many security vulnerabilities. In some cases, COTS technologies may be incorporated with little effort while, in some others, profound adaptations or even specifically developed technology, meeting military requirements, will be needed.

Concerning the nature of tactical networks, we refer to the work conducted by NATO groups IST-090 and IST-118 that we introduce next.

Incorporating Web-based Technologies in Tactical Networks

Tactical networks can be defined as the communications infrastructure for the low-level forces that operate in the battlefield. It connects deployed command posts with mobile units and covers communications down to the individual soldier. Tactical networks are formed in disadvantaged grids that, as defined by the NATO IST-090 Task Group, exhibit one or more of the following characteristics: limited bandwidth, variable throughput, unreliable connectivity and energy constraints imposed by the wireless communications grid that links the nodes (IST-090, 2014). As opposed to tactical networks, the Internet - and its associated protocols and technologies - relies on stable broadband infrastructures (broadband, low latency and stable).

Based on (Manso *et al.*, 2015), Table 1 presents the main differentiating characteristics between stable broadband infrastructures (present in telecommunications and strategic/high-level military networks), tactical legacy networks (e.g., VHF and UHF radios) and tactical wireless broadband mobile networks (WBMN). Colour codes and font weight are used to represent the following: Green cell and bold text to represent a positive attribute; Pink cell to represent a negative attribute. For example, a static topology makes for a stable network environment and is deemed positive, whereas a mobile topology poses challenges with e.g., disconnections and is hence deemed a negative attribute.

Network Type / Network Characteristic	Strategic Military Networks	Mobile Tactical Networks (Legacy)	Mobile Tactical Networks (WBMN)
Topology	Static / Fixed Topology	Mobile / Dynamic Topology	Mobile / Dynamic Topology
Data Capacity	Broadband (>Mbps)	Narrowband (~Kbps)	Wideband / Broadband (>Mbps)
Latency	Low	High	Variable (Low to High)
Reliability	Reliable (assumed always connected)	Unreliable (connectivity loss, need to reconnect)	Unreliable (connectivity loss, need to reconnect)
Reach	Global	Mostly Local (Team level)	Mostly Local (Team level)
Transmission Mode	Bi-directional	Simplex or half-duplex	Bi-directional

Table 1 - Network characteristics for strategic networks and tactical networks. Source: (Manso et al., 2015)

It becomes evident that attempting to directly apply Internet principles and concepts - such as IoT and web-based technologies - in Tactical Networks is not devoid of challenges:

- Tactical WBMN exhibit sufficient characteristics to explore the application of IoT and Internet-based technologies given their bi-directional capability (allow using most Web services protocols) and high data throughput (allow “data intensive” services, such as high-definition video exchange). However, the variable latency (e.g., risk of TCP timeout) and connection unreliability (e.g., risk of packet retransmissions resulting in traffic increase) may require protocol selection, adaptation and *profiling*.

- The characteristics of tactical legacy networks (narrowband, unreliable, simplex/half-duplex) make the application of Internet-based technologies unfeasible. Herein, the use of low resource protocols and technologies (non web-based) should be considered.

The IST-090 Task Group and the follow-on IST-118 (IST-118, 2013) and IST-150 (recently started and currently active) groups took the task to identify challenges in and demonstrate the application of Internet-based technologies, specifically Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) at the tactical level. Specifically, the groups have demonstrated the capability to use SOA and Internet-based technologies at the tactical level, identified advantages and disadvantages of used SOA solutions, and produced adaptations recommendations to the protocol stack (e.g., use of connection-less (e.g., UDP), packet timeout increase, or delay tolerant protocols, use compression for packet size reduction). Lessons learned and recommendations are applicable for this work as well.

Communications

Realizing a robust connected force requires communications enabling data exchange among components. As presented before, military forces rely on specialized highly secure radios to interconnect forces. Military radios are known to privilege security and robustness over performance, resulting in poor data exchange throughput, for example.

Commercially available communications technologies provide many interesting features for FSS deployed in "friendly" or "neutral" environments, where there is an acceptable level of risk in connecting devices to existing communications infrastructures and the detection of RF emission devices can be tolerated. Table 2 presents communications technologies that are relevant for this work, including their characteristics.

Technology	3G	4G/LTE	WiFi	BLE	LPWA (e.g., LoRA)
Range	tens of kms	tens of kms	dozens of meters	few meters	several kms
Power (while Tx)	1.5 - 3 W	1.2 - 3.3 W	0.06 - 1.2 W	0.1 W	0.06 - 0.21 W
Operation Time	2 - 4 hours	2 - 3 hours	4 - 8 hours	months to years	months to years
Energy Harvesting	No	No	No	Possible	Possible
Throughput (peak upload / download in Mbps)	5 / 100	500 / 1024	600	0.27 - 1	0.05 / 0.28

Table 2 - Communications Technologies Characteristics. Adapted from (Lake, 2016)

Different communications technologies offer specific features to meet specific needs:

- Cellular (e.g., 2G, 3G and 4G/LTE) provide long range (several kms) but require an infrastructure (i.e., base stations owned by telecommunications operators). 4G/LTE in particular provides broadband connectivity (up to 1Gbps) and is capable of supporting bandwidth intensive services (such as video streaming).
- WiFi is widely supported, offers broadband (several Mbps) but only works in close-range (dozens of meters).
- For low range personal networks, a widely popular technology is Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) that favours low-power consumption over data speed.
- Leveraged by the IoT industry, Low Power Wide Area (LPWA) include interesting emerging technologies for low-power, long-range (several kms) and narrowband (few Kbps) communications.

Table 3 summarises a possible selection of communications to meet a specific purpose.

Communications Technologies Purpose	Digital 4G/LTE (trusted infrastructure)	Wi-Fi	Bluetooth LE	LoRA
HQ-squad communications	X			
Intra-squad communications	X	X		
Devices carried by soldier			X	
IoT devices (unattended, low throughput required)				X
IoT devices (unattended, high throughput required)	X	X		

Table 3 - Communications Choices per Device Type

Security considerations

The adoption of widely available COTS-based technology for military purposes raises many concerns in what regards security and trust. The civil market aims for easy-to-use functionalities that sometimes are achieved by sacrificing security aspects. Furthermore, it is well known that many service providers profit by exploiting user information (including age, gender, location and usage patterns) collected from devices.

In addition, the software running in devices may become, at some point, compromised. The following recent incidents illustrate this point:

- The HummingBad malware, associated with Chinese cyber criminals, infected millions of Android devices to generate millions of dollars of fake ad revenue¹.
- More recently, Kryptowire discovered a backdoor in budget Android phones that secretly sends information like text messages, location data and call logs to a server in China².
- More specifically concerning IoT and smart devices, the Mirai botnet exploited known security vulnerabilities in IoT devices (weak or known admin passwords) to infect more than 2.5 million devices, including routers, IP cameras, DVRs and Printers. The Mirai botnet was able to control them and trigger a distributed denial of service (DDoS) attack that mainly affected the Dyn registration service provider, disrupting services provided by Twitter, Netflix, Spotify, Reddit, and many others³.

This is not to say that such devices should not be used, but instead that security aspects should be carefully assessed and mitigation measures implemented. Best practices need to be implemented, such as select trusted manufacturers, install applications developed by trusted providers only, always install the latest security updates, verify installed software, use antivirus software, perform adaptations and configurations in the operating system to raise privacy, use end-to-end encryption and disable unnecessary communications (e.g., Bluetooth). Furthermore, it is important to give proper thought on the classification of data that such devices should be able to handle, and apply the necessary measures to ensure an acceptable level of trust to the system. Here, it must be considered the different ownership models that may come into play. Ranging from *Bring Your Own Device* (BYOD) to specially

¹ <http://www.techrepublic.com/article/hummingbad-malware-infected-10-million-android-devices-millions-more-at-risk/>

² <http://www.techrepublic.com/article/android-backdoor-is-secretly-sending-user-data-and-texts-to-china-and-no-one-knows-why/>

³ <https://www.theverge.com/2016/10/21/13362354/dyn-dns-ddos-attack-cause-outage-status-explained>

tailored COTS solutions, different needs can be accommodated by different systems. BYOD is the cheapest approach, but its trust level is also the lowest. Still, BYOD is a viable approach for certain applications, which is why NATO is currently developing a BYOD security policy (Armando *et al.*, 2016).

FFI SMART Experiment

FFI conducted several initiatives exploring the use of COTS to support operational missions, to obtain cost-effective solutions and to experiment the introduction of novel services. An example is the FFI PISA prototype in which an Application developed for Android and iOS allowed users to report positions and incidents to a central headquarters, but did not allow any data to be shared back to them (Krog *et al.*, 2015). PISA provided an untrusted tool for information gathering but not dissemination. The work has moved to the Android platform with a prototype supporting "trusted unclassified" communications consisting on a collection of third-party applications and an application developed in-house. The concept, which was aptly named "SMART", was evaluated with the Norwegian Home Guard in a series of technical trials and culminating with an operational use during a national exercise (Johnsen *et al.*, 2017). The SMART project's main goal was to enable pervasive situational awareness on the individual soldier level by leveraging low-cost, low-complexity consumer electronics in a concept prototype delivering trusted unclassified communications.

The Norwegian Home Guard, or "Heimevernet" (HV), is one of five branches of the Norwegian Armed Forces and serves as a quick reaction force. Their main responsibility is territorial protection. HV consists of more than 45 000 soldiers distributed in four regions, 11 districts and 241 areas covering all of Norway⁴. HV is a mobilization force (i.e., the soldiers are not employed by the military on a daily basis, but train on a regular basis) consisting of 15 Rapid-reaction Intervention Forces (RrIF) and 241 Area Forces (AF). While the RrIF are capable of rapid response and consist of highly trained and equipped personnel, the AF have longer reaction time, are less equipped and the personnel receives less training.

The SMART prototype complements current national classified capacities, strengthening the situational awareness capabilities of the HV AF. This is in contrast to other existing systems - such as DINA⁵ - that are targeted more towards special operations and army forces requiring handling of classified communications and thus must run on accredited and trusted platforms. SMART, on the other hand, has BYOD as its baseline for unclassified communications for the Area Forces. Hence, it is clear that there is a need for at least two different system approaches, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Classified vs. Trusted unclassified suggested deployment and use

⁴ <http://forsvaret.no/en/organisation/home-guard>

⁵ <http://www.teleplanglobe.no/defence/dina>

Results of the work presented in this paper will be proposed as extensions to the SMART concept, representing a significant increase in functionalities and information sharing. Using an existing prototype for concept development and early trial work instead of an accredited system is both appropriate and convenient, since the latter is cumbersome and too "rigid" for this stage of the work, and best done when the concept has been operationally proven.

3 Concept

In this chapter, a novel concept in applying smart devices and IoT to FSS at the tactical domain is addressed. As reference, it is used the HV AF use case and the results from the SMART prototype experiment. Overall, the concept aims to improve situational awareness at the individual soldier level, as well as significantly increase functionalities and sharing of information (concerning soldiers and the surrounding environment).

Use Case: Deployed Area Forces of the Norwegian Home Guard

In a deployed scenario, the HV AF is constituted by several squads, each comprising a group of typically 5 soldiers. Each squad is under the coordination of a squad leader. The squad leader responsibilities include coordinating the mission (requiring high levels of situational awareness, including "real-time" location of assets, ISR reports and tracking of goals) as well as assessing the soldiers' status and the safety of the squad. At the HV AF level (headquarters), responsibilities include coordination and management of all deployed squads, including their location, status, ISR reports and accomplishment of goals.

Depicted in Figure 2, the force, squads and soldiers become fully connected and share information in order to improve overall situational awareness at soldier, squad and force level.

Figure 2 - Fully Connected Force

Smart Devices for FSS

This paper addresses the soldier level, which is also the most relevant one for the application of smart devices. IoT concepts and smart devices can be used to provide, with a high degree of automation, mission critical information including location (of soldiers and assets), soldier health status, and location of suspicious/hostile entities and presence of dangerous substances (e.g., chemical agents) in the intervention area. Furthermore, information collection devices - such as cameras - can be used to provide *intelligence* / points-of-interest in multimedia form (e.g., high-resolution photos taken from a device) and human reports. Finally, a robust connected force can subscribe to all (mission relevant) information being published and, supported by proper displaying capabilities, generate a high-level of shared situational awareness across all force.

In Table 4, it is presented a non-exhaustive mapping between functions relevant in operational scenarios and devices that may support them.

FSS Function	Supporting Devices
Geolocation	GNSS receiver MIMU (i.e., magnetometer, 3-axis accelerometer, 3-axis gyroscope) Barometer/altimeter RF sources (e.g., Wi-Fi router location)
Body orientation	MIMU
Activity Tracking / Motion information	IMU (i.e., 3-axis accelerometer, 3-axis gyroscope) GNSS receiver
Hit / Fall Indication	IMU
Health status	Heart Rate monitor Respiratory Rate monitor Body Temperature
Biometric Authentication	Fingerprint sensor Face recognition (using camera)
ISR	Imagery and Video ((ultra) high-definition camera) Audio (microphone) Reports (files)
Environmental information	Temperature sensor Humidity sensor Air quality sensor (e.g., concentration of CO, CO2, Propane, ...)
CBRN information	C, B, R and N sensors

Table 4 - Mapping of FSS Function to COTS components

A simple but illustrative example on the use of the accelerometer - as a smart device - to generate information at the soldier level is presented next.

Accelerometer applications for FSS: A 3-axis accelerometer measures the acceleration of the body that it is attached to a 3 axis (XYZ). It has many applications in consumer electronics, such as activity tracking. Its characteristic to measure the Earth’s gravity force allows determining orientation (roll, pitch and yaw) of a body and body segments. Properly fused with data from a 3-axis gyroscope and a magnetometer, the accelerometer can be used to provide location updates (especially useful in GNSS-denial zones). In the context of FSS, accelerometers can be used to detect and characterize motion, update location information, detect falls and determine a soldier posture (e.g., standing up, lying in floor). In addition, a strong acceleration peak might indicate a hit (e.g., shot indication).

The amount of devices that can be used to support FSS functions is vast. Many of these can be found in consumer products - such as smartphones (see Table 5) and wearables (e.g., smartwatches) - as well in emergent technologies, such as smart textiles.

Machine to Machine

A core aspect in IoT relies in the machine-to-machine (M2M) capability, that is, information exchange directly between devices, not necessarily involving human interaction. M2M can be achieved through a message broker middleware based on the publish-subscribe paradigm.

The NATO IST-118 Group has demonstrated the use of SOA publish-subscribe Web Services Notification (WS-Notification)⁶ at the tactical level. The WS-Notification has the benefit of being a NATO recommended standard for information exchange in a coalition environment. However, it is a resource heavy protocol and its application at the tactical level requires applying proprietary optimizations (IST-118, 2013). More recently, as part of the SMART prototype, the REST approach was used to post and retrieve data. However, certain functionalities - such as event-based notification and message retransmission - are not provided by REST and need to be implemented. More recently, the IST-150 Group conducted initial experiments comparing different publish-subscribe approaches on tactical broadband radios. Namely, WS-Notification, Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) were investigated in a preliminary small-scale study (Bloebaum and Johnsen, 2015). Here, MQTT was found to be a very lightweight alternative to the other two protocols when applied in the tactical network. Consequently, MQTT is the chosen M2M publish-subscribe mechanism for this stage of work and it is briefly described next.

MQTT is a popular publish-subscribe middleware in IoT standardized as ISO/IEC PRF 20922 (ISO/IEC 20922:2016). MQTT is a lightweight Client Server publish-subscribe messaging transport protocol originally developed out of IBM's pervasive computing team, but has moved to the open source community and seen a significant growth in popularity. MQTT provides publish-subscribe messaging for resource-constrained devices. The resource constraints can be related to low processing power, low memory and low power, as well as network constraints. In addition, MQTT was designed to cope with low bandwidth and intermittent networks, characteristics present in tactical networks.

MQTT follows a server-client architecture and a topic-based approach for information. The MQTT-server is the entity that manages topics within a network of MQTT-clients. Access to topics may require authentication. MQTT-clients can define topics and publish information (messages) to topics. Furthermore, MQTT-clients can subscribe to specific topics (or group of topics, according to MQTT rules) and, benefitting from MQTT, automatically receive notifications when messages are published. Figure 3 illustrates the MQTT publish-subscribe mechanism.

⁶ https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=wsn

Figure 3 - MQTT Publish-Subscribe Paradigm

MQTT is designed to work well on unreliable networks and, as such, provides three levels of Quality of Service (QoS) for different situations:

- QoS Level 0 ("At most once"): messages are delivered according to the best efforts of the operating environment. Message loss can occur.
- QoS Level 1 ("At least once"): messages are assured to arrive but duplicates can occur, hence systems must be able to handle duplicate packets.
- QoS Level 2 ("Exactly once"): where message are assured to arrive exactly once. This method requires an exchange of four packets, and will decrease performance of the broker.

4 Implementation and Deployment

In this chapter, the first steps for the implementation process of a proof-of-concept (PoC) exploring smart devices, COTS technologies and IoT concepts are explained. The PoC goal is to demonstrate the capability to exchange device data between nodes, that is, soldiers and the headquarters. For this purpose, a simple version of the "blue force tracking" (BFT) service is implemented as follows: each connected node periodically sends its location information and receives location information of all connected nodes.

The selected mobile platform is a COTS Android smartphone that already incorporates several sensor components (smart devices), display, processing and communications capabilities. Also very important in the Android platform is the easiness to develop, integrate and install software components. Finally, using Android brings compatibility with the SMART prototype developed by FFI.

Table 5 presents the specifications of an Android smartphone, including featured components.

Smartphone	Component	Characteristic
<p>Source: https://www.google.com/nexus/</p>	Processor	Qualcomm® Snapdragon™ 810 v2.1, 2.0 GHz octa-core 64-bit Adreno 430 GPU
	Memory	3GB RAM up to 128GB
	Display	5.7" (1440 x 2560 pixels, ~518 ppi pixel density)
	Camera	Rear: 12.3 MP; 1.55 μm; f/2.0 Front: 8 MP Video: 2160p@30fps, 720p@240fps
	Communications	Cellular (2G, 3G and 4G) WiFi (IEEE 801.11 a/b/g/n/ac), Bluetooth, NFC
	Location	GNSS: GPS, A-GPS, GLONASS
	Sensors	Fingerprint MIMU (accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer) Proximity Barometer
	Other	Flashlight

Table 5 - Smartphone Specifications and Devices

For this PoC, the smartphone's most relevant capability is to determine location information, achieved through the GNSS receivers. Also relevant is the capability to exchange data. For this purpose, the smartphone's cellular capabilities (4G) or, if available, WiFi connectivity is employed.

To demonstrate the functionalities, a mobile application (App) prototype has been developed, supporting the following functions:

- Retrieve geolocation data from the phone GNSS device;
- Publish location messages via its MQTT-client;
- Receive location messages pertaining to the whole squad via its MQTT-client;
- Display location of squad in a local map.

In addition, a simple Java desktop application prototype has been implemented, supporting the following functions:

- Receive location messages pertaining to the whole squad via its MQTT-client;
- Display location of squad assets in a local map.

Finally, a MQTT-server has been deployed by FFI and made accessible for this experiment.

Figure 4 presents a high level view of the deployment. In this setting, a squad is deployed comprising 9 soldiers (1 being the squad leader). Each soldier carries a smartphone running the App prototype. At the top level, the HV AF headquarters run the desktop prototype. Location information is shared and shown to all force elements.

Figure 4 - Fully Connected Force: Overview of Deployed Architecture

A central element in the prototype is the MQTT topic-based middleware. In order to uniquely index services (and thus associated messages), the following topic structure was created:

```
/country-Id/squad-Id/soldier-Id/service-type
```

Where:

- "country-Id" uniquely identifies the country. For example, according to the NATO STANAG 1059, "NOR" is used for Norway.
- "squad-Id" is an arbitrary string that uniquely identifies the squad.
- "soldier-Id" is an arbitrary string that uniquely identifies the soldier.
- "service-type" is a string that uniquely identifies the type of service. For example, "location" is used to access information publish pertaining to soldier location (in latitude and longitude).

Considering a single squad with 4 soldiers (one being squad leader), the following configuration can be used:

Soldier	Topic Name
Soldier 1 (Squad Leader)	/nor/squad-001/soldier-001
Soldier 2	/nor/squad-001/soldier-002
Soldier 3	/nor/squad-001/soldier-003
Soldier 4	/nor/squad-001/soldier-004

Under each "soldier", the subtopic "location" is created representing the service used to provide the soldier location and thus used for the BFT service.

Whenever a soldier's location changes, a message containing the updated location is published. Since location messages are produced periodically, use of "QoS Level 0" (at most once) is recommended. The message payload is formatted as XML, according to the schema presented next.

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```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!--
  FFI test format for IoT sensor data exchange version 1.0
  Source identification and sensor type is deduced from the topic structure
  The information is published on so that only actual data is included
  fields:
    longitude          (optional) - position, if applicable
    latitude           (optional) - position, if applicable
    altitude           (optional) - position, if applicable
    timestamp          (optional) - date and time of sensor information, if applicable
    numericData        (optional) - numeric sensor data, if applicable
    textData           (optional) - text, if applicable
    rawData            (optional) - base64 encoded binary sensor data, if applicable
-->

<xsd:schema xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" xmlns="urn:ffi:IoT:1:0"
targetNamespace="urn:ffi:IoT:1:0" elementFormDefault="qualified" xml:lang="en">
  <xsd:element name="data">
    <xsd:complexType>
      <xsd:sequence>
        <xsd:element name="latitude" type="xsd:double" minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
        <xsd:element name="longitude" type="xsd:double" minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
        <xsd:element name="altitude" type="xsd:double" minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
        <!-- ISO 8601 for date and time representation in the format YYYYMMDDhhmmss
format (14 digits) -->
        <xsd:element name="timestamp" minOccurs="0">
          <xsd:simpleType>
            <xsd:restriction base="xsd:string">
              <xsd:pattern value="\d{14}"/>
            </xsd:restriction>
          </xsd:simpleType>
        </xsd:element>
        <xsd:element name="numericData" type="xsd:double" minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
        <xsd:element name="textData" type="xsd:string" minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
        <xsd:element name="rawData" type="xsd:base64Binary"
minOccurs="0"/></xsd:element>
      </xsd:sequence>
    </xsd:complexType>
  </xsd:element>
</xsd:schema>
```

Thus, for example, when solder-001 changes location, the following message is published to topic "/nor/squad-001/soldier-001/location":

```
<data xmlns='urn:ffi:IoT:1:0'>
  <latitude>38.7223</latitude>
  <longitude>9.1393</longitude>
  <timestamp>20170514221107</timestamp>
</data>
```

For the demonstrator, a mix of real and simulated nodes was used, according to the setup presented in Table 6.

Node	Real/Simulated	Topic Name (Location updates)	Period
Headquarters	Real	Not applicable	Not applicable
Soldier 1	Real (smartphone)	/nor/squad-001/soldier-001/location	On change
Soldier 2	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-002/location	One second
Soldier 3	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-003/location	One second
Soldier 4	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-004/location	One second
Soldier 5	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-005/location	One second

Soldier 6	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-006/location	One second
Soldier 7	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-007/location	One second
Soldier 8	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-008/location	One second
Soldier 9	Simulated	/nor/squad-001/soldier-009/location	One second

Table 6 - Setup used for demonstrator

MQTT provides a convenient syntax by means of wildcards allowing a client to subscribe to multiple topics. As such, in order to receive location updates from all squad, clients issue the following subscription:

```
/nor/squad-001/+/location
```

Figure 5 presents several snapshots taken throughout the execution of the deployment. The prototype successfully presented and updated all nodes' location on a map (represented by blue rectangles). The desktop version includes a blue line representing historical information, allowing visualizing the node's trajectory progression over time.

With this setup, it is confirmed that the configuration was successful in sharing and updating location information each second. It is also confirmed that the MQTT server was able to meet the data demand (MQTT CPU load was mostly below 1%), which was not surprising considering the small number of clients (10) and low publishing frequency (1 Hz). It was also observed that the network traffic with one location subscriber (about 2.5 kbps) and two location subscribers (6.5 kbps) indicated the MQTT network load to be indeed low. Still, a large-scale deployment of hundreds of nodes needs to be analysed in future steps.

Headquarters View 1 (Desktop)

Headquarters View 2 (Desktop)

Headquarters View 3 (Desktop)

Headquarters View 4 (Desktop)

Solder View 1 (App)

Map credits: © OpenStreetMap contributors

Figure 5 - Concept Demonstrator Snapshots

5 Conclusion

This paper presents the first steps taken in the incorporation of smart devices, COTS and IoT concepts in FSS. Using as reference the Norwegian Home Guard Area Force use case and prior work conducted with FFI's SMART prototype, a first proof-of-concept (PoC) implementation proposes a novel concept, implemented through the use of MQTT, smartphones and a desktop application. The PoC successfully demonstrated the BFT service using 9 mobile nodes and one fixed node (as Headquarters). Furthermore, it was confirmed that, for the configuration used, MQTT produced a low footprint, both regarding CPU and network load.

The PoC findings established important foundations for the next steps of this work that will include:

- Adaptation to the context of the FSS and NATO of rules and ontologies representing IoT resources, entities and services following existing standards and best practices (such as SensorML⁷ and IoT-Lite Ontology⁸).
- Increased PoC functionalities and incorporation of additional smart devices and functions, such as those as listed in Table 4.
- Demonstration and evaluation of PoC scalability in large-scale deployment scenarios, involving the deployment of hundreds of nodes publishing and subscribing information, including also the implementation of appropriate information filters and functional hierarchies.
- Demonstration and evaluation of PoC robustness by varying network conditions (e.g., availability and performance).
- Incorporation of components in FFI's SMART concept, aiming towards real-live demonstration and evaluation of concepts.

In addition, the implementation of future steps will consider the constraints in mobile devices and IoT-related equipment with limited computational power, energy requirements and network performance, namely for tactical environments. Examples of the constraints to be addressed are:

- Appropriate use of components and network: to reduce the use of GNSS components and wireless communications for these consume significant energy and their use is likely to reduce a device's operation time to only a few hours.
- Appropriate update of frequencies for sensors and services: producing sensor data at high frequencies may congest the network and several updates do not really represent added value to existing information.
- Appropriate selection and configuration of components and protocols: to ensure adequate performance at device and system levels.
- Strategies to reduce network traffic: available options include the aggregation of data from multiple components and the production of a single message (the trade-off message size vs. messages transmitted needs to be determined).

Particularly relevant for the next steps in the work to assess the application of smart devices and IoT to FSS at the tactical domain is the ongoing collaboration with NATO Groups, namely the NATO IST-150, which is conducting experiments with MQTT in the context of military operations, tactical networks and NATO interoperability.

⁷ <http://www.sensorml.com>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/Submission/iot-lite/>

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